

Heining, K. and Egert, U.

Simulated impact of increased rates of high-load bursts on background rates of low-load bursts

Commentary on

Heining K, Kiliyas A, Janz P, Häussler U, Kumar A, Haas CA, Egert U (2019) Bursts with high and low load of epileptiform spikes show context-dependent correlations in epileptic mice.

eNeuro:[10.1523/ENEURO.0299-18.2019](https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0299-18.2019), DOI:10.1523/ENEURO.0299-18.2019.

In previous discussions, it had been suggested that the anti-correlations we describe in Heining et al. (2019) between the rate of high-load bursts and the background rate of low-load bursts might be trivial because in sessions with many high-load bursts – and thus shorter intervals between them – there would be no time left for low-load bursts; hence the rate of low-load bursts should be lower in such sessions. This is, however, not the case, as we illustrate below. Since it is an illustration more than a control experiment or so, we did not add it as supplementary data to the manuscript but nonetheless would like to make it available to interested readers.

In the paper, we specifically evaluated the rate of low-load bursts in background phases only. High-load and transition phases were excluded from the rate calculation. Having more high-load bursts would replace some low-load bursts with high-load bursts of appropriate duration. The simulation presented here shows that overwriting low-load bursts with high-load bursts shortens background phases but has effectively no impact on the average rate of low-load bursts during these phases and cannot generate the (anti-)correlations we observe.

Panels **(A–C)** show examples of our simulations for different rates of high-load bursts. We generated a 2.5 h series of low-load bursts with Poissonian interval distribution ('background process'). The rate of low-load bursts in this background process (1.2/min) matched the average rate of low-load bursts across all background phases from our dataset (first traces in A–C show a 20 min example section). We then generated a series of high-load bursts with Poissonian interval distributions (second traces in A–C) and superimposed these on the background process such that a high-load burst annihilated any overlapping low-load bursts (third traces in A–C, overwritten low-load bursts are marked). The distributions of the durations of low-load and high-load burst were matched to those in our recordings. We next delimited 'background phases', in this simulation defined as the intervals between high-load bursts (fourth traces in A–C), and calculated the rate of low-load bursts for each background phase individually and averaged across all background phases (shown in A only). This average was weighted by the duration of the corresponding background phase. Note that in (A) the rate of low-load bursts averaged across background phases is 1.2/min, exactly the rate of the original background process (top trace in A). In (A) the rate of the high-load events is relatively low, hence there are comparatively few and long background phases. In (C) the rate of high-load bursts is high, obviously resulting in more and shorter background phases. **(D)** Rate of high-load bursts plotted against duration of background phases. Durations of individual background phases are shown in gray, the average across each simulation is shown in black. Red dots mark simulations belonging to the examples shown in (A–C). As the rate of high-load bursts increases, background phases become shorter on average. **(E)** Rate of high-load bursts plotted against the rate of low-load bursts averaged across all background phases from a simulation. The background rate of low-load bursts is independent of the rate of high-load bursts (compare to Figure 6A in Heining et al. 2019). This clearly demonstrates that the anti-correlation we observe between the rate of high-load and the background rate of low-load bursts in our recordings is indeed non-trivial.

Simulated impact of increasing rate of high-load bursts on the background rate of low-load bursts

A example 1: high-load bursts: 0.2 /min

B example 2: high-load bursts: 0.5 /min

C example 3: high-load bursts: 0.8 /min

